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GROWING GAP BETWEEN SECONDARY EDUCATION AND ENGINEERING BACHELORS IN FLANDERS: SPECIFIC SHORTCOMINGS AND CAUSES

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ABSTRACT

Over the past decade, teachers in the first-year of the Engineering bachelor program at KU Leuven have experienced a decline in the incoming students prior knowledge and understanding of STEM subjects and mathematics in particular. To study the perceived growing gap between actual and expected prior knowledge, first year students and tutors at the KU Leuven Faculty of Engineering Science were questioned. 500 students completed an anonymous online survey targeted at their first semester results, prior education and experienced difficulties in the transition from secondary to higher education. Interviews with 7 tutors aimed at getting a deeper understanding of specific shortcomings in prior knowledge and understanding. Results indicate that particular mathematical topics, such as complex numbers and differential equations, are expected knowledge when enrolling in the Engineering program but are rarely treated at sufficient depth in Flanders secondary schools. While the majority of students indicate to be satisfied with their secondary education, many still point out a lack of exercises, applications and depth of understanding. Other significant factors are the acquired study approaches, and time and stress management skills. Both inquiries confirm the mismatch between expectations by Flanders Engineering faculties and what is achieved at the secondary level. Secondary curricula, teaching methods and academic environments are said to have a direct influence on this mismatch. This warrants further research into the underlying teaching methods, guidance and curricula at the secondary and university level.

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Problem statement and context

Professors, teaching assistants, and tutors at Flemish faculties of Engineering Science have noticed a steady decline in the level of prior scientific and mathematical knowledge in first year bachelor students. This exposes a gap between Flemish secondary education and the Engineering bachelor in Flanders that has been noticed since 2008 [1]. Additionally, a similar gap is noticed in other higher education STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) fields [1]. A lack of prior scientific and mathematical knowledge has negative implications for both students and faculty members. Students have to 'bridge' the gap, which takes time and negatively impacts their motivation [2]. Tutors, on the other hand, receive increased requests for counselling, which is increasing their work load and forces them to explore increasingly creative methods to provide qualitative guidance to all students who are in need. Considering the relevancy and severity of this issue, the different Faculties of Engineering Sciences in Flanders, initiated dialogues with the Flemish secondary educational organisations and local teacher training departments. The aim of this cooperation is to decrease the gap between both secondary education and university engineering education. Within this context, the need for a clear description of the problem arises. Both higher education institutes and secondary education schools require a clear definition of the problem related to the gap between both educational levels. This exploratory study aims at providing such a clear description, focused on mathematics and interdisciplinary projects. Mathematics has a significant role in all major STEM fields. Interdisciplinary projects combine application of theoretical concepts and integration of multiple subjects, which characterizes most engineering disciplines. The presented research scope is limited to the KU Leuven Faculty of Engineering Science. This faculty hosts two principal bachelor programs: Engineering (Ir.) and Engineering-Architecture (Ir.-Arch.), along with a multitude of specialized master programs.

1.2 Research questions

The aim of this research is to accurately describe the discrepancy between Flemish secondary education and the first year of local Engineering bachelor programs. Specifically, the mismatch with regards to mathematical course contents and problems regarding study methods and attitudes are studied in order to answer the following questions. How do students experience the transition from secondary school to an engineering bachelor? What problems, in terms of study methods and attitudes, are experienced by students? What mathematical topics do students struggle with? How do these problems relate to prior secondary education? What are the underlying causes at higher levels of education?

2 METHODOLOGY

In order to answer the questions put forward, this paper uses an exploratory approach. To this end two groups were surveyed: first year students and academic tutors at the KU Leuven faculty of Engineering Science. It is expected that tutors' viewpoints potentially allow to observe an evolution in time, especially considering the long-term employment contracts of the tutors, whereas student experience may only offer a snapshot building on their own experience.

Seven tutors of the KU Leuven Faculty of Engineering Science were interviewed in a one-on-one setting. All tutors were involved in the support of different first-year Engineering and Engineering-Architecture courses and across the seven tutors, all first-year classes of the faculty were covered. Tutor interviews took place in a period of one month before the student survey was presented.

During the interviews, the discussion was left open as much as possible but four key questions

guided all conversations:

1. When students consult you, what problems are you approached with?
2. What are, according to you, their principal challenges that students encounter?
3. How can KU Leuven help to remedy these problems?
4. How can Flemish secondary institutions help remedy these problems?

Notes were taken during these interviews and tutor's answers were subsequently compared to each other. Close attention was paid to highly similar and directly contrary opinions.

First-year students at the KU Leuven Faculty of Engineering Sciences were questioned in the form of an anonymous online survey. The survey was presented in the first week of the second semester of 2020-2021. This timing offered students time to reflect on their results of the first semester, the study techniques they applied, and any difficulties they may have encountered. Additionally, this survey questioned them about their prior experiences in secondary education, including: prevalence of (interdisciplinary) projects in these past years; specific mathematical subjects; studying techniques; time and stress management; and personal appreciation for their secondary formation. Subsequent processing of the results was aimed at:

1. Relating the hours of mathematics students had in secondary education with their scores during the first exam period.
2. Relating the presence of certain math topics in secondary curricula with their scores during the first exam period.
3. Exploring overall student satisfaction with regards to their secondary education and specific contributions to this satisfaction.
4. Exploring students' perception on studying methods and attitudes.

The anonymous survey was filled in by 500 students, henceforth referred to as the sample group. This group consisted of 425 students enrolled in the Engineering (Ir.) bachelor and 75 students following the Engineering-Architecture (Ir.-Arch.) bachelor. These numbers correspond to approximately 90% of first-year students for both programs.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Tutor interviews

None of the seven interviews revealed any conflicting viewpoints or opinions. All results and answers are summarized in the following paragraphs. The tutors perceive a significant mismatch between the level that is achieved in Flemish secondary education and what students are expected to master at the start of the Engineering(-Architecture) bachelor program at KU Leuven. Different tutors also note that, even if current secondary curricular goals are fully achieved, a gap between both levels still exists. The existing gap is, at least partially, due to high expectations in Flemish university curricula. The root causes here are believed to be twofold. On one hand, tutors feel that university teaching staff is not sufficiently aware of secondary education curricula, especially if they have been subject to changes. On the other hand, professors and engineering programs as a whole are often reluctant to make changes or additions to university curricula as this would reduce the available time for what currently are principal engineering subjects and taking into account the expectations of the work-field of graduating engineers.

Tutors indicate that students struggle to gain sufficient insight in these engineering topics, possibly due to lack of abstract reasoning skills and a lack of contextualized examples. A multitude of potential causes are stated by tutors. First, there is the evolution of Flemish secondary curricula away from theory and towards alternative assignments and teaching methods. Consequently, secondary education textbooks contain less theory and a lower level of

abstraction. Specifically, textbooks are also stated to contain very few contextualized examples, i.e. exercises in the context of a real life application. Secondly, teachers in secondary education face serious challenges due to strict limitations of teachers' classroom instruction and evaluation to not exceed course curricula. Thirdly, heterogeneous class groups, make it difficult to challenge all students in a single class, while providing sufficient time for support. Finally, the training of younger teachers puts a greater emphasis on newer, less theoretically strict teaching methods.

Tutors also note that, as the scope of study narrows in the academic bachelor, course contents become more profound. The accompanying (mathematical) concepts are also more complex and students allegedly have trouble understanding and discerning between these concepts. According to tutors, the increased complexity is not the only problem. Available learning materials at this level are often written in a more rigorous, scientific manner, which is in contrast to more didactic materials in secondary education. Specifically, the contrast between closely related concepts is not sufficiently emphasized in university textbooks and lectures, leading to confusion among students.

Time and stress management also present challenges to students. Higher education presents the students with relative freedom and independence as many students move away from home and to the university city. In addition, the pedagogical structure, including frequent evaluation, provided by secondary education, is mostly replaced by planned but non-mandatory lectures and fewer evaluation periods per academic year. Sufficient discipline is required from students and this is not always cultivated in the prior context of secondary schooling. This is believed to be especially problematic for students who are above average in intelligence, e.g. many students starting at Engineering faculties. Many of these gifted students rarely had to exert themselves during secondary education and hence, may lack the discipline to study independently or to constructively cope with academic setbacks. For these students, failure to achieve a given goal may be new and this may prove to be very demotivating and stressful. Hence, some of the tutors again point to the importance of sufficiently challenging all students in secondary education but also to the importance of cultivating discipline and motivation in this context.

Students are observed to adopt relatively superficial study methods. Tutors believe that this is closely related to the point mentioned in the previous paragraph. Deep understanding of a subject requires sufficient theoretical study along with repeated exercise. Students often neglect to go through the steps of reflective problem solving and prefer to consult existing solutions for similar problems. This may be due to lack of discipline, lack of time, or both. Superficial strategies used by students only require a minimum of profound understanding. Tutors state that their advice often underlines the importance of solving problems step by step and (semi-)independently. The rise of social media and online document sharing platforms have worsened this issue, as solutions can be exchanged more easily.

A final issue noted by the tutors, stems from students and parents ignoring advice related to academic pathways. Starting in Flemish secondary education, students receive recommendations with respect to their academic level and potentially, other disciplines that may be better suited for the given student. However, students are often still enrolled in disciplines that are more renowned or perceived as prestigious, like STEM fields of study and those intended to prepare them for a higher education. Such programs do not always match the students' interests and competences and such status-driven orientation is rarely to the benefit of the student. A similar attitude is appearing at the KU Leuven faculty of Engineering Science where students in a remedial academic track may choose to ignore tutor advice with respect to re-orientation or lower course enrolment. Again, the image of certain programs and personal pride play a

significant role in these decisions.

3.2 Student survey

The majority of enrolled students, i.e. 479 students indicated that they had completed general secondary education (GSE), specifically meant to prepare students for higher education. The remaining 21 students followed a technical (TSE) program. Within both groups, students may have had between 4 to 8 hours of mathematics per week. However, programs with 6 to 8 hours of mathematics dominate the sample group, with 493 students.

When reviewing their secondary education with regard to the extent to which it prepared them for the first semester in the Engineering(-Architecture) bachelor, students were fairly satisfied. Results, displayed in figure 1, show that almost 70% of all students at least agreed that secondary education had prepared them sufficiently for the bachelor. In comparison with students in the Engineering bachelor, students in the Engineering-Architecture bachelor seemed to be less satisfied with their secondary education. During the tutor interviews, an idea surfaced that may explain this small difference. Generally, students starting in the Ir.-Arch. bachelor, expect this program to be less difficult than the Ir. program. This is however not the case as engineering architecture requires good abstract mathematical and scientific reasoning and design skills.

Figure 1: Extent to which secondary education prepared students for an Engineering(-Architecture) program, as indicated by students

Students were presented with open questions about what specific factors influence their satisfaction with their secondary education. Two categories were considered: a first set of factors, related to course contents and hard skills on one hand and a second set of factors related to student attitudes and studying techniques on the other. With regard to course contents, students were overwhelmingly positive about their acquired basics in mathematics, approximately 40% of students list their secondary mathematics training as a direct positive contribution to their preparation for higher education. Other positive contributions are said to be: developing abstract reasoning skills; developing a mindset for (mathematical) problem solving and presence of good teachers. Do note however, that this is in contrast to tutor opinion. Student opinions were mixed with regards to other scientific subjects. An approximately equal amount of students list secondary physics and chemistry courses as either positive or negative contributions to their preparation for the engineering bachelor. Students reflect negatively on: an insufficient depth of understanding that is developed and offered at the secondary level; a large difference in pace between secondary and university levels; and a substantive difference between what is taught in secondary and higher education. These remarks aligned with comments by tutors.

When considering other factors, students mostly indicated that proper time management skills were acquired during secondary education. Overwhelming praise was also attributed to both cooperative skill and independence in an academic context. Opinions were mixed related to studying techniques and work ethics. A part of the sample group showed awareness of poor working discipline or superficial study methods.

Mathematical knowledge and treated topics were questioned in more depth in the survey. Results indicated that students may feel under-prepared for certain engineering topics. Specifically: differential equations, vectors, matrices, spatial geometry, and complex numbers were less covered in Flemish secondary education. Figure 2 shows this indication by students, ranging from "not treated" to "very well prepared", for the listed topics.

Figure 2: Extent to which secondary education prepared students for mathematical topics, as indicated by students

First semester results for the engineering bachelor in 2021 were in accordance with previous academic years and their distribution is shown in figure 3. A distinction was made between the following grade categories: intolerable (0-7), failed but tolerable (8-9), sufficient (10-13), very good (14-20). Results for Calculus and Applied Mechanics were rather poor with well over 50% of students failing these subjects. Results for Applied Chemistry show just below half of the students failing. Students performed better in Algebra and the project course, with 78% and 90% passing rates respectively.

Figure 3: 2021 First semester results as reported by students, for Engineering bachelor

When accounting for prior education, differences in score arise. Here, results for the Ir-Arch. bachelor are neglected as it leads to insufficient student numbers per category to be statistically relevant. Figure 4 shows the distribution of scores per Ir.-bachelor subject, for all students with a history in TSE and 8 hours of mathematics or GSE and 6-8 hours of mathematics. The data shows that students coming from a GSE program with 8 hours of mathematics performed better than their peers in all engineering bachelor subjects. Similarly, former TSE students perform relatively worse in all subjects, even when compared to former GSE students who had less hours of mathematics. Their poor scores in math and science subjects were remarkable and may be due to a different focus in TSE math classes. Additional factors, such as different attitudes and science subjects in secondary education warrant further exploration.

Figure 4: 2021 First semester results as reported by students, for the engineering bachelor, per subject and number of hours of mathematics per week in secondary education

When looking at the prevalence of interdisciplinary and group projects in secondary education, it appeared that only 13% of students had project work in secondary education, yet scores for the Ir. bachelor project course were exceptionally good when compared to other first semester courses. It should be noted however that this course followed very different teaching and grading methods than the more conventional non-project-based courses.

4 DISCUSSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Within the scope of broader dialogues between Flemish secondary educational and KU Leuven's and engineering faculty, the gap between both levels of education is identified through interviews with university tutors and a survey of first-year university students at the KU Leuven Faculty of Engineering Science. Students and tutors confirm the existence of a gap between Flemish secondary education and programs at the KU Leuven Faculty of Engineering Science. We believe that the results from this exploratory study can be extended to apply for enrolling students in other Flemish Engineering faculties. In relation to the transition from secondary schooling to higher engineering education, students indicate to be satisfied with their secondary education. Many students state that they have a strong mathematical basis although this is not entirely reflected in their first semester bachelor results. Students and tutors indicate that students experience a structural pedagogic difference between both levels of education. Support is reported to be less available and evaluation is less frequent in higher education Engineering programs as compared to secondary education. It is concluded that this cultural and structural transition, along with more complex and profound course contents present a steep learning curve for first-year students. With regards to differences in pedagogic structure, students' learning methods and attitudes play a significant role. Students do note shortcomings with regard to study methods and study attitude. Applied study methods are often deemed too superficial by tutors and both tutors and students note that discipline, to

tackle the challenges of higher engineering education, may be problematic for students. Hence, tutors believe that emphasizing the cultivation of proper studying techniques and discipline could be of great benefit for many students. This potential is further supported by previous findings [3], stating that learning skills and motivation are a necessary condition for success in STEM fields. Student survey results are further interpreted to imply that students with a technical secondary background especially suffer from this pedagogic transition. Hence additional attention to this group may prove to be promising, even if these students currently only comprise a small part of all first year students at Engineering faculties in Flanders. The student survey indicates relatively low scores for the first semester Engineering bachelor courses. We believe this is closely related to the reportedly treated topics in secondary mathematics education. According to students, differential equations, vectors, matrices and complex numbers are, often not sufficiently treated in secondary education. These topics hold a significant role in first year Engineering faculty courses, specifically in Calculus (differential equations, complex numbers) and Mechanics (vector and matrix manipulation), and more generally in modelling and problem solving applications. Tutors did not significantly comment on specific topics but do agree that mathematics on a secondary level remains too superficial. There is said to be insufficient attention for abstraction in terms of theory and exercises are said to lack practical and realistic context. Students do not report this shortcoming when questioned but may possibly not realize that a lack of contextualized exercises is part of the underlying problem.

Further conversations will be organized with education experts, specifically in the field of student tutoring and professional teacher training, to explore ways to close the gap between expectations in secondary education and those in university Engineering programs. We believe that an effective and sustainable way to equip students with the required knowledge and attitudes, is to focus on professional development of STEM teachers in secondary education [4]. As suggested by this study, such professional development should address teaching practices with regard to mathematical and scientific topics that are important in engineering, as well as practices regarding contextualized problem-solving and abstract thinking. In the broader scope of this ongoing research, further discussions between secondary and higher education teachers may uncover other strategies on how to match these desired practices with secondary STEM curricula

The Flemish secondary education system is currently also undergoing a reformation, with the introduction of new programs, also in STEM fields. This includes the development of technical, STEM oriented programs that also serve as preparation for higher education. This evolution is monitored closely by Engineering faculty staff and may prove to be an effective way of improving students' prior knowledge and college readiness.

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